

THE INTERRELATED EFFECT OF SCHOOL CONTEXT DOMAINS ON THE MATHEMATICS PRODUCTIVE DISPOSITION OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the significant effect of School Context domains on the Mathematics Productive Disposition. A predictive- correlation research design was used in this study. The respondents of this research study were 244 junior high school students in Kapatungan National High School, who were identified using stratified random sampling and fishbowl draw or lottery method. The researchers utilized a questionnaire adopted from Akey (2006) for the School Context, and the second instrument, the mathematics productive disposition questionnaire was adopted from Awofala (2022). Mean, Pearson r and Multiple Linear Regression were used as statistical tools to attain this study's objectives. Results revealed that the School Context and Mathematics Disposition of the respondents was high. This means that the School Context and Productive disposition of the was evident in Kapatungan National High School. There is also a strong positive relationship between School Context and Productive disposition. Lastly, predictors of School Context namely, Active Learning Strategy, student-to-student interaction, and Making Connections and Extension have significant effects on the Mathematics Productive Disposition of the students and can be modeled using the $Y=0.172X_1+ 0.214X_2+0.158X_3+5.069$.

Keywords: *School Context, Mathematics Productive Disposition, Predictive-Correlational Design, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The concept of mathematical disposition entails an individual's deeply held attitudes and behaviors regarding mathematics. It encompasses their beliefs about the logic, utility, and significance of mathematics in everyday life and various contexts. (Kusmaryono et.al.,2019)). Despite that, Mathematics still becomes the most hated and not enjoyable subject in school. Many junior high school students fail to enjoy mathematics classes, not because of being lack of ability, but rather due to their negative disposition or perception towards mathematics. Teachers are challenged to transform their negative mathematical disposition into positive (productive) mathematical disposition so that they trust in mathematical power and function to solve problems and for their future career progress (Cai et.al., 2012). Like many junior high school students around the world, Kapatungan National High School students frequently find it difficult to enjoy math studies. The primary cause of this is not a lack of mathematical aptitude, but rather unfavorable attitudes or beliefs about the topic.

Students require dispositions to encourage perseverance in challenging problems, responsibility for learning, and the development of good work habits in mathematics. It is said school context significantly influences students' productive dispositions in mathematics, with teachers' facilitation efforts affecting students' autonomy, beliefs, and focus on understanding (Gilbert, 2014). Thus, fostering dispositions to mathematics through training improves prospective Filipino teachers' and students' performance. Teachers who care about their student's academic achievements and are willing to exert the effort needed to ensure that the classroom is a fruitful learning setting have features that may not be measured as possession of instructional knowledge and skills. These are teachers, who through their actions and character, are establishing effective teaching dispositions (Llagas Jr., 2021).

Numerous studies have shown that students' learning outcomes are influenced by the schools they attend, as well as their home and community environments. Despite extensive research on various aspects of school context and mathematical disposition, much of the existing literature has focused on variations in instructional techniques, often emphasizing direct, factual teaching methods (Graham, 2024). Therefore, this study aims to explore how the relationship between students' school context can impact their productive disposition, particularly in the local context. Additionally, this study highlights the impact of school context on the mathematical productive disposition among junior high school students at Kapatungan National High School.

Consequently, studies have shown that many students experience a mathematical productive disposition that is influenced by their school environment, which can limit their learning potential and hinder their ability to excel in international settings. Thus, the researchers perceive that there is a need to conduct the study to determine the significant effect of School Context on the Mathematics Productive Disposition of Junior High School Students.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to determine the significant effect of School Context on Mathematics Productive Disposition among Junior High School Students in Kapatungan National High School (2022-2023).

Specifically, this study aimed to attain the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of school context in terms of:
 - 1.1 Academic Expectations;
 - 1.2 Conduct Expectations;
 - 1.3 Active Learning Strategies;
 - 1.4 Students-to-Student Interactions; and
 - 1.5 Making Connections and Extensions.
2. To determine the level of student's Mathematics Productive Disposition in terms of:
 - 2.1 Mathematical Integrity;
 - 2.2 Affect;
 - 2.3 Beliefs;
 - 2.4 Identity;
 - 2.5 Risk Taking;
 - 2.6 Goals;
 - 2.7 Motivation; and
 - 2.8 Self-efficacy;
3. To determine the significant relationship between School Context and Mathematics Productive Disposition.
4. To determine the significant effect of School Context domains on the Mathematics Productive Disposition.

METHODOLOGY

This study used the predictive- correlation research design to determine if a predictive effect exists of school context on the mathematics productive disposition among junior high school students. The predictive correlation research design predicts the variance of one or more variables based on the variance of another variable(s). The respondents of the study were the 244 junior high school students, in Kapatungan National High School who were enrolled in the third quarter of academic year 2022-2023. The study participants were chosen through universal sampling. The research instrument used in this study consisted of two sets of questionnaires: one on school context and another on mathematics productive disposition. The questionnaire for School Context was adopted from Akey (2006) while the Productive Disposition questionnaire for Mathematics was adopted from Awofala (2022). Finally, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation and Regression Analysis were employed to achieve the study's objectives.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of School Context among the Students of Kapatungan National High School

School Context	Mean	Description
Academic Expectation	2.29	High
Conduct expectation	3.19	High
Active Learning Strategy	2.85	High
Student-to-student Interaction	2.75	High
Making Connection and Extension	3.04	High
Overall Mean	2.95	High

Table 2. Level of Mathematics Productive Disposition of Students in Kapatungan National High School.

Mathematics Productive Disposition	Mean	Description
Affect	3.14	High
Identity	3.08	High
Mathematical Integrity	3.12	High
Risk-Taking	3.00	High
Goals	3.20	High
Motivation	3.15	High
Self-Efficacy	2.91	High
Overall Mean	2.95	High

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Level of School Context and Mathematics Productive Disposition.

School Context	Mathematics Productive Disposition		
	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Academic Expectation	0.451	0.000	Highly Significant
Conduct Expectation	0.520	0.000	Highly Significant
Active Learning Strategies	0.543	0.000	Highly Significant
Student-to-Student Interaction	0.559	0.000	Highly Significant
Making Connection and Extension	0.422	0.000	Highly Significant
Overall	0.656	0.03	Highly Significant

Table 4. The Effect of School Context on the Mathematics Productive Disposition of Junior High School Students in Kapatungan National High School

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients	p-value	Remarks
Constant	1.042	0.000	Highly Significant
Academic Expectations	-0.012	0.892	Not Significant
Conduct Expectations	0.115	0.100	Highly Significant
Active Learning Strategies	0.172	0.017	Highly Significant
Students-to-Student Interactions	0.214	0.001	Highly Significant
Making Connections and Extensions	0.056	0.005	Highly Significant
r²	0.140		
F	58.35		
p	0.000		

DISCUSSION

The level of School Context among the students of Kapatungan National High School. Overall, it obtained a mean value of 3.12, which means that the School Context level is high. This means that the School Context is evident. The result signifies that the students have a positive classroom environment. It is widely understood that schools do not have sole responsibility for enabling all these learning outcomes for students. Home and community contexts contribute significantly to students' schooling experiences and their learning outcomes (Thrupp & Lupton, 2013). In addition, the first indicator of Academic Expectation obtained a mean of 2.96, perceived as high by students. The remaining indicators also scored high means, ranging from 3.11 to 3.19. This suggests that these factors moderately influence the quality of students' learning. Quality practices inside the classroom and across the school play a critical role in providing learning opportunities and creating environments for student success (Wang & Eccles, 2013).

On the other hand, the level of Mathematics Productive Disposition, as perceived by the students in Kapatungan National High School, obtained a mean value of 3.09, which means that the level of Mathematics Productive Disposition is high. This means that Mathematics Productive Disposition is evident. It implies that students are apparent as they work towards their academic goals in Mathematics. Increasing the productive

disposition of students needs to be done so that students are enthusiastic about learning mathematics (Haji, 2019). Moreover, the indicators of Mathematics Productive Disposition, including Goals, Motivation, Affect, Mathematical Integrity, Beliefs, Identity, Risk Taking, and Self-Efficacy, all showed moderate levels. This suggests that students are motivated to learn Mathematics despite some negative dispositions. The indicator of self-efficacy was demonstrated at a high level, indicating that students have confidence in their mathematics abilities. This aligns with the findings of previous research (Cribbs et.al., 2015).

With regards to the relationship between the School Context and Mathematics Productive Disposition using Pearson R Correlation. As shown, an overall r-value obtained 0.65 with a p-value of 0.00, which means that there is a strong positive relationship between the two variables. This implies that any increase in the variance of the school context corresponds to an increase in mathematics disposition variance. Students who demonstrate productive dispositions are better positioned to engage effectively with mathematics (Jansen, 2012).

The Linear Regression Analysis in Determining the Significant Effect of School Context on the Mathematics Productive Disposition of Junior High School shows that the domains of School Context, namely Active Learning Strategy, Student-to-student Interaction, and Making Connection and Extension have a significant effect on Mathematics Productive Disposition with the p-value less than 0.05. It means that these indicators can affect the Mathematics Productive Disposition of the Students in Kapatungan National High School. The equation is summarized as $Y=0.172X_1+0.214X_2+0.158X_3+5.069$ where Y is the Mathematics Productive Disposition, X_1 refers to Active Learning Strategy, X_2 refers to Student-to-Students Interaction and X_3 refers to Making Connection and Extension. This implies that if the other variables as constant, the following interpretation will follow. First, for every 1 unit in the Active Learning Strategy will have a corresponding 0.172 unit increase in Mathematics Productive Disposition, for every 1 unit increase of Student-to-Students Interaction will have a corresponding increase of 0.214 in Mathematics Productive Disposition, and for every 1 unit increase of Making Connection and Extension has corresponding 0.158 increase in Mathematics Productive Disposition. Agommuoh and Ifeanacho (2013) said that Mathematics knowledge equips students with skills to analyze and change the world. This can be achieved through the learners as their mental faculty is stimulated to solve problems, discover the best possible solutions, and enable learners to think independently in applied and abstract ways which in turn assists in solving problems and assessing various risks. Students who possess high self-confidence in mathematics tend to believe in their abilities and that they can be successful in learning and eventually passing the subjects as their confidence helps them to overcome the fear of failing. These students dare to take mathematical challenges which in turn increase their academic achievement.

Moreover, based on the r^2 significant the overall Predictor of School Context namely; Active Learning Strategy, Student-to-student Interaction, and Making Connection and Extension has 44 % contribute to Mathematics Productive Disposition. This further

implies that the remaining 56% may come from other variables not included in this study. In such situations, they are required to exhibit a set of prosocial skills that enable equitable interactions within the group so that mathematical reasoning can take place (Wilkerson, 2017).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the School Context was now evident. Second, Mathematics' Productive Disposition was evident. Furthermore, it was found that changes in the variance of School Context correspond to changes in the variance of Mathematics Productive Disposition. If the other variables are held constant, the following interpretations can be made. Firstly, for every 1 unit increase in Active Learning Strategy, there will be a corresponding 0.172 unit increase in Mathematics Productive Disposition. Secondly, for every 1 unit increase in Student-to-Student Interaction, there will be a corresponding increase of 0.214 in Mathematics Productive Disposition. Lastly, for every 1 unit increase in Making Connection and Extension, there will be a corresponding 0.158 increase in Mathematics Productive Disposition. These factors contribute to 44% of the Mathematics Productive Disposition, implying that the remaining 56% is not covered in the study.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. The principal should plan to generate programs and orientation to obtain new strategies and techniques which the students prefer to increase their performance and achievement in academics and they should try to create a conducive environment for students to learn and enjoy mathematics subject.
2. The students should also participate with the principal and teachers to generate relevant teaching strategies. They must identify how they prefer to learn and know which indicators of student attitude and behavior greatly affect them in the Mathematics Productive Disposition.
3. Faculty should raise awareness in motivation in mathematics since it is only moderate level compared to the School Context is in moderate level which means that faculty should and teachers be accompanied by negative factors such as disengaged or unsupportive teachers or a negative school culture, it may hurt student's Productive Disposition towards Mathematics.
4. Future researchers, since the study has a big percentage of significant effect, may use this study to add to the body of knowledge that may be useful in conducting their study related to School Context and Mathematics Productive Disposition.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to ethical guidelines set by the ASSCAT and followed the steps below in the gathering of data.

Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study. The researchers secure permission through a formal letter that addresses to the Principal of Kapatungan National High School to gather the needed information.

Conduct of the Study. After the approval of the letter, the researchers immediately gathered the list of the Junior High School students who are enrolled in the school year 2022-2023 to determine the population and sample size of this study. The request will be directly administered to the survey so that the researchers can attend to conduct the survey questionnaire on the selected respondents. The data gathered will be collected and recorded in coordination with the satisfaction. The researcher ensured that respondents were well-oriented as to the mere purpose of the instrument and assured that the data gathered would be treated with the utmost confidentiality.

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